

SYNTHESIS OF 3-(*p*-HYDROXYPHENYL)-CYCLOHEXANONE.

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A synthesis of 3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone, which consists of a hydrogenated diphenyl nucleus, has been described. The above ketone was expected to be oestrogenically active, but experimental results according to Allen-Doisy test were found to be negative up to the maximum dose of 8 mg.

In course of an investigation on the possible oestrus-producing activity of synthetic substances (Cook *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **114B**, 272, 286), made the important discovery that the oestrogenic activity is extraordinarily unspecific and that the oestrus change can be induced by numerous substances bearing little resemblance to the hormone itself. In their earlier investigations, one of the simplest substances to be found oestrogenically active was 1-keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydrophenanthrene (*Naturwiss.*, 1933, **21**, 222 ; *Nature*, 1933, **131**, 56, 205) and the first active compound, in which the phenanthrene nucleus was absent was found to be 1 : 2-dihydroxy-1 : 2-di- α -naphthylacenaphthene (*Nature*, 1936, **137**, 996). Simpler molecules were then studied and substances such as 4 : 4'-dihydroxydiphenyl, *p*-hydroxypropenylbenzene (Dodds and Lawson, *Nature*, 1937, **139**, 627, 1068 *et seq.*) were also found to possess oestrogenic activity. From consideration of the above it seemed to be of interest to investigate the physiological property of the ketone (I).

(I)

The present communication deals with a method for the synthesis of the above ketone. Ethyl γ -anisoylbutyrate (II) has been treated with zinc

and ethyl bromoacetate in benzene solution to yield the lactone of α -carbethoxy-2-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-2-hydroxypentane-5-carboxylic acid (III). β -(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-pimelic acid (IV) is obtained by reducing the above lactone with zinc dust and 10% sodium hydroxide solution. Both the ethyl and methyl esters of the dibasic acid (IV) are cyclised by means of sodium in benzene solution. The resulting crude β -ketonic ester, which, however, could not be distilled without decomposition in vacuum, yields on hydrolysis with 20% sulphuric acid 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (V). 3-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I) is obtained by demethylation of the above methoxyketone with hydrobromic acid.

The above compound is found in the Allen-Doisy test to be inactive up to the dose of 8 mg., when injected into castrated mice. In this connection, however, the work of Butenandt and Schramm (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 2083, 2303), who prepared the γ -hydroxy derivative of 1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene, may be mentioned. Their ketone is also found inactive in the Allen-Doisy test up to 9 mg.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl γ -Anisoylbutyrate (II).— γ -Anisoylbutyric acid was prepared by modifying the method of Plant and Tomlinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 856). To an ice-cold solution of finely powdered dry aluminium chloride (70 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (250 c.c.), was added dropwise with constant shaking a mixture of glutaric anhydride (30 g.) and anisole (30 g.). The thick red coloured mass was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 48 hours, and then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. Nitrobenzene was removed by steam distillation, when γ -anisoylglutaric acid separated in fine crystals on cooling and was filtered off. The crude product was purified by dissolving in sodium bicarbonate solution and acidification. The acid (50 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of ethyl alcohol (200 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 12 c.c.) for 6 hours on a boiling water-bath. The ester was isolated in the usual manner, when it boiled at 193–95°/5–6 mm., as a colourless liquid, which quickly solidified and on crystallisation from ethyl alcohol separated in white needles, m.p. 59–60°. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 7.08. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 7.2 per cent). The *semicarbazone* on crystallisation from ethyl alcohol melted at 120–21°. (Found: N, 13.66. $C_{15}H_{21}O_4N_3$ requires N, 13.68 per cent).

*Lactone of 1-Carboethoxy-2-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-2-hydroxypentane-5-carboxylic Acid* (III).—The keto-ester (II) (42 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (42 g., 1.5 mols) and zinc wool (21 g.) in dry benzene (120 c.c.) were taken in a flask provided with an efficient reflux condenser and heated on a water-bath, with the addition of a crystal of iodine. The reaction started after about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and grew vigorous, when it was necessary to remove the flask from the water-bath. After the vigorous reaction had subsided, the flask was replaced on the water-bath and the heating was continued for further 2 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed with ice and dilute sulphuric acid. The benzene layer was washed with water and then extracted with 10% sodium carbonate solution, in which the δ -lactone dissolved freely in the cold. The alkaline solution was acidified and extracted with ether.

The extract was washed with water and dried. Ether was removed and the lactone was distilled at $229\text{--}30^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 35 g. (Found: C, 65.61; H, 7.15. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 65.75; H, 6.84 per cent).

β -(p-Methoxyphenyl)-pimelic Acid (IV).—A solution of the lactone (20 g.) in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (500 c.c.) was placed in a two-necked flask, provided with a reflux condenser and a mercury-sealed stirring arrangement. Zinc dust (75 g.) was added to the solution and the contents were heated to boiling and mechanically stirred for 18 hours. The zinc was filtered off and an excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid added to the filtrate. The white precipitate, thus obtained, was filtered off and redissolved in 10% sodium carbonate solution. The solution was filtered off from undissolved impurities and acidified. The dibasic acid, so obtained, was collected, washed well with water, dried and crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol, m.p. $154\text{--}56^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 63.22; H, 6.78. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 63.15; H, 6.76 per cent). For the preparation of diethyl and dimethyl esters of the acid (IV), the following method was used. The crude acid, obtained by acidification of the filtered alkaline solution, was extracted with benzene, and the benzene layer well dried over sodium sulphate. The residue, left after removal of benzene, was refluxed with ethyl or methyl alcohol (100 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 10 c.c.) for 12 hours. On working up in the usual manner, the diethyl ester was collected at $195\text{--}205^{\circ}/4\text{--}5$ mm. and redistilled at $199\text{--}201^{\circ}/4\text{--}5$ mm. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 7.83. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 67.08; H, 8.07 per cent). The dimethyl ester was also collected at $187\text{--}95^{\circ}/4\text{--}5$ mm., and redistilled at $190\text{--}93^{\circ}/4\text{--}5$ mm. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 7.37. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 65.3; H, 7.48 per cent).

3-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (V).—Dimethyl *β -(p-Methoxyphenyl)-pimelate* (7.3 g.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) was refluxed with sodium dust (1.1 g.) until all the sodium went into solution (*ca.* 2 hours). The solution was cooled and treated with ice and dilute sulphuric acid. The benzene layer was separated and washed successively with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water and dried. The benzene was removed and on attempting to distil the oil, it was found to decompose. The crude oil, which gave a reddish violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, was refluxed with an excess of 20% sulphuric acid for 12 hours. The resulting oil was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed with water and dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and the ether removed. The residual brown oil on distillation in vacuum solidified. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether ($40\text{--}60^{\circ}$), m.p. 83° . (Found: C, 76.28; H, 7.76. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.47; H, 7.84 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* of the above ketone, on crystallisation from ethyl alcohol, melted at 217-19°. (Found : N, 16.02. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 16.09 per cent).

3-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I).—The methoxyketone (V) (1.5 g.) was heated with acetic acid (23 c.c.) and hydrobromic acid (23 c.c., d 1.49) at 110° for 3-4 hours. The cooled solution was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and the hydroxy-ketone was extracted by shaking it with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. After acidifying the alkaline solution, the hydroxy-compound was taken up in ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried and the ether removed. The residue, on distillation in vacuum, solidified to a yellow crystalline mass, m.p. 155-58°. On recrystallisation from benzene it melted at 159-61°. (Found : C, 75.69 ; H, 7.28. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.78 ; H, 7.36 per cent).

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